

Effectiveness of a Group Psychological Intervention to Enhance Student Subjective Well-being of High School Students at Pathein, Myanmar: A Mixed-method Study

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For this study, the researcher explores the effectiveness of a psychological intervention specifically tailored for Burmese high school students from Pathein to increase their well-being. In this paper, well-being is defined as joyful learning, school connectedness, education purpose, and academic self-efficacy. The researcher used explanatory sequential mixed-method design for this study. There is a total of 170 high school students who participated in this study and were randomly divided into experimental and control groups. Then, the researcher customized a 45-minute group intervention sessions which included gratitude exercises, affirmations, vision boards, goal-setting exercises using the PERMA framework. To assess well-being of students, the Student Subjective Well-being Questionnaire (SSWQ) was implemented before and after the intervention. After collecting quantitative data, 15 participants from the experimental group were chosen for semi-structured interviews to understand lived experiences. According to the quantitative results, the experimental group showed significantly higher well-being scores after the intervention in all four components of well-being compared to the control group ($p < .05$). Large effect sizes are also reported, especially in academic self-efficacy, meaning the intervention is effective and practical. From the qualitative findings, there are five themes from the participants: clarification of their purpose of studying and personal goals, feeling optimistic and motivated toward schoolwork, better regulation of their own emotions, increased school-related engagement, and improving social connections with peers. These findings suggest that culturally adaptable positive psychological intervention is needed for young adults in Myanmar to improve their well-being. Integrating these results into school can increase resilience, well-being, educational purpose, and reduce loneliness.

Keywords: Adolescent well-being, psychological intervention, positive psychology, school-based mental health

Mental health concerns in adolescents are increasing worldwide, especially in middle-income and low-income countries. Many adolescents in Myanmar are facing mental health problems such as depression and anxiety. According to Carroll (2021), up to 30% of adolescents have mental health problems, and more than 20% show symptoms of depression. One out of ten adolescents admitted that they have considered suicide. Just by looking at these data, it can be seen that culturally adapted mental health programs are urgently needed for young adults in Myanmar.

In addition, adolescents in Myanmar are experiencing many mental health challenges due to prolonged school closures during the pandemic, limited resources to health care systems, and cultural stigma. Although many young adults are struggling with mental

problems, it is not easy for them to ask for help because of fear of judgement and limited awareness about mental health. Apart from these reasons, ongoing political unrest ignites stress and trauma in adolescents since 2021. Many young adults have to cope with school closures, civil war, and uncertainty about their own future (UNICEF, 2021) which are contributing factors in adolescents' mental health problems.

When mental health problems remain untreated, there can be many serious consequences such as poor academic performance, drug abuse, social withdrawal, and the risk of emerging serious mental health problems (WHO, 2022). In addition, adolescence is a period where identity development is important, and a stage where social connection and academic learning are practiced (Branje, 2022). Therefore, supporting mental health at this stage is crucial to ensure positive individual outcomes and community well-being.

In spite of the need for mental health support programs for adolescents, there are still very few effective programs. Although school-based interventions are considered to be effective globally (Waters, 2011) they are still an uncommon practice in Myanmar, especially in school settings. Existing programs do not consider cultural values and language barriers, and they also have limited resources, which impact the effectiveness of those programs (Carroll et al., 2021). The researcher noticed that there is very little research on evidence-based interventions for school settings, which are also culturally adaptable.

This gap shows the importance of developing culturally adapted

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mental health programs, which are also aligned with evidence-based practices. Therefore, the researcher aimed to develop programs which can increase students' positive emotions about school, relationship building, purpose of learning, and goal-setting. Schools are the best place for implementing mental health programs because they can reach a large number of students efficiently and affordably, contributing to public health goals and community development.

This study focuses on this gap by developing a culturally adapted positive psychology group intervention for high school students in Pathein, Myanmar. In this study, Seligman's PERMA model (2011) was used to cultivate positive emotion, relationship connection, meaning of learning, and accomplishment. The intervention activities include gratitude exercises, journaling, affirmations, vision boards, and SMART goal-setting. The intervention program was reviewed by experts and pilot-testing was also done to achieve relevance culturally and population-wise.

For this study, explanatory sequential mixed-methods design was used, providing both quantitative data and qualitative insights into personal experiences of students. This method helps us to understand the effectiveness of the intervention through quantitative data and also helps us to give further proof why this intervention works in this context. The results can contribute to various sectors such as school counselors, educators, policymakers, and mental health professionals because this intervention is culturally adapted and practical in Myanmar high school settings. Overall, this research aimed to encourage adolescent well-being, educational achievement, and resilience in low-resource settings.

Objective of the Study

To examine the effectiveness of a culturally adapted group psychological intervention in enhancing student subjective well-being, including joyful learning, school connectedness, educational purpose, and academic self-efficacy.

Method

Study Design

In this study, the researcher used an explanatory sequential mixed-

methods design to examine the effectiveness of a well-being psychological intervention among high school students in Pathein, Myanmar. This design was used to provide quantitative evidence of intervention effectiveness and qualitative insights into students' lived experiences (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).

Phase 1 is a pretest-posttest control group design, which allows measurement of the amount of change in subjective well-being. The design is beneficial for educational settings where random assignments can be challenging, yet comparing groups is still possible (Robbins et al., 2012). Phase 2 consists of a semi-structured interview with a subset of participants from the experimental group. This design can explore how students experienced the intervention to contextualize the quantitative results (Ivankova, Creswell, & Stick, 2006).

Participants

Participants were Grade 10-12 high school students, who were 15 to 18 years old from a private school in Pathein, Myanmar. The researcher collaborated with school authorities, teachers, and parents for recruitment. After obtaining ethical clearance, the researcher clearly explained the study purpose, steps of procedures, and voluntary nature of participation to participants. After that, informed consent forms were distributed in English and Burmese versions to students and parents. In this study, non-probability convenience sampling method was used due to some considerations such as schedules of students, their availability, and logistical concerns. Although convenience sampling method limits generalization, it is a feasible method in low-resource settings (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016). At first, 180 participants volunteered for this program, but later, 10 participants were excluded due to their absence in intervention sessions. So, the final sample consists of 170 participants, and they were randomly assigned to experimental group ($n=85$) and control group ($n=85$). In the experimental group, there were 55.3% of males and 44.7% of females, whereas there were 41.2% of male and 58.8% of female students in the control group.

Intervention Development. To develop a culturally adaptable intervention, the following step by step guidelines were processed to ensure both theory grounding and feasibility:

Step	Description
1. Review	The researcher conducted a comprehensive existing positive psychology theories and evidence-based researches to ensure the intervention is theoretically grounded and relevant to students' needs.
2. Module Design and Development:	The module includes four main activities such as gratitude exercises, affirmations, vision boards, and SMART goal setting based on PERMA framework.
3. Expert Consultation	The researcher consulted with experts and got feedbacks from them to ensure content validity, cultural sensitivity, and theoretical alignment.
4. Pilot Testing	For this step, two students and one observer were asked for feedbacks after testing the module with them to make sure of feasibility and effectiveness.
5. Final Refinement	Revised and finalized the module according to participants and observer to ensure high educational value, engagement, and clarity.

Intervention Content and Delivery. The duration of the intervention sessions was 45-minute online sessions, conducted via Zoom application due to political situations in Myanmar. A total of 4

sessions were delivered over one month. Each component of subjective well-being defined by Student Subjective Well-being Questionnaire (SSWQ) was addressed in each session:

Joyful Learning: Promotes positive feelings about learning by doing gratitude exercises.

School Connectedness: Promotes relationships through affirmations.

Educational Purpose: Promotes a sense of meaning and goals through vision boards.

Academic Self-Efficacy: Promotes academic performance via SMART goal setting.

Session 1: Joyful Learning

In this session, the researcher taught participants gratitude exercises such as journaling, appreciating positive aspects of daily life, and noticing personal strengths. The goal of this session is to improve positive emotions and awareness of good things in their lives. Moreover, gratitude practices are also related to improved well-being and reduced stress (Emmons & McCullough, 2003). The researcher also encouraged students to write gratitude letters to someone such as teachers or peers. Then, their feelings and experiences about this activity were discussed in a small group.

Session 2: School Connectedness

For this session, the researcher used affirmations to improve self-confidence, motivation, and bonding with peers. Students learned what affirmations are and learned to create their own. They practiced writing or saying affirmations out loud. The researcher also guided students to personalize affirmations to their own goals and shared positive statements about peers. This practice helped to increase a sense of belonging and well-being, with evidence of linking to school connectedness (Arif et al., 2019).

Session 3: Educational Purpose

The researcher utilized vision boards in this session to clarify goals and find meaning in the learning process for the participants. Students learned the concept of visioning their future to improve motivation and daily habits. Then, they discussed and created a vision board that includes future goals, motivational phrases, and areas they want to improve. Finally, the researcher encouraged students to reflect and share within a group.

Session 4: Academic Self-Efficacy

For this session, the researcher introduced SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, time-bound) goals to participants. The goal of this session is to help students set structured, achievable goals within a certain time period. The group discussed personal goals, an action plan, and possible challenges in the session. The researcher used this method because it is found that clear, achievable goals can enhance self-efficacy and academic performance according to goal-setting theory (Bandura, 1997; Zimmerman, 2000).

Finally, to measure well-being scores of the students, the researcher used Student Subjective Wellbeing Questionnaire (SSWQ). It is a self-report questionnaire and includes 16 items which have strong internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = .781$). Each item uses a 4-point Likert scale (1 = Almost Never, 4 = Almost Always). The SSWQ was translated into Burmese by professionals following Brislin's (1970) back-translation procedure. To make sure of accuracy and comprehension, the researcher presented both English and Burmese versions to participants.

Data Collection and Data Analysis

For quantitative data, the researcher collected pre-test data one week

before the intervention and collected post-test data one week after the final session of the intervention. The data were collected via online forms and securely stored to protect confidentiality of the participants. For qualitative data, 15 participants from the experimental group were purposively contacted for semi-structured interviews. Sampling was based on post-test SSWQ scores to secure diversity of experience (Ivankova et al., 2006). The researcher included participants with high, moderate, and low post-intervention SSWQ scores for interviews, and gender and age were all balanced. The researcher conducted interviews via Zoom and made sure safety and convenience of the participants. Each session lasted approximately 30 to 45 minutes approximately. Interviews followed a guide that explored participant experiences of the intervention, perceived effectiveness, challenges encountered, and suggestions for improvement. Last but not least, informed consent for audio recording and transcription was also obtained.

For the data analysis part, quantitative data were analyzed with SPSS software and independent samples t-tests were applied to compare pre-test scores and post-test scores between experimental groups and control groups. Qualitative data were transcribed, translated, and analyzed thematically using Braun and Clarke's six-phase framework, with manual coding to ensure accuracy.

Results

Quantitative Findings

In this study, quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design was used to compare well-being scores between the experimental group and the control group. The student's well-being scores were measured by using the SSWQ questionnaire. Baseline scores between two groups before the intervention showed no difference except for slightly higher school connectedness in the experimental group, that was considered in interpretation. The post-intervention results showed significant improvement in the experimental group across all four domains of well-being. Effect sizes were large for overall well-being ($d=0.99$), joyful learning ($d=0.94$), and academic self-efficacy ($d=1.19$), with medium effects for school connectedness ($d=0.50$) and small-to-medium effects for educational purpose ($d=0.36$). These results prove the hypothesis that the conducted intervention has a significant impact on the subjective well-being of high school students in Myanmar.

Qualitative Findings

The qualitative part of the study used semi-structured interviews with 15 participants from the experimental group. Through thematic analysis, five themes emerged: (1) clarification of their purpose of studying and personal goals, (2) feeling optimistic and motivated toward schoolwork, (3) better regulation of their own emotion, (4) increased school-related engagement, and (5) improving social connection with peers. Participants also shared some challenges such as shyness and difficulty in setting specific goals but they said they can overcome those challenges with the help of a supportive group environment.

By integrating both data types, the study shows that the intervention caused measurable improvements in well-being and meaningful personal change for adolescents. Students also shared that they felt more motivated, experienced more positive emotions, built stronger relationships, and gained greater confidence, proving the intervention's effectiveness for supporting adolescent mental health within Myanmar's school setting.

Discussion

According to previous empirical research, positive psychological interventions have been tested to improve well-being and engagement among adolescents. Based on the results of this study, the intervention significantly improved all four well-being domains, which means positive psychological intervention was effective in enhancing well-being of Myanmar high school students (Bolier et al., 2013; Waters, 2011). There is very little empirical research on positive psychological intervention among Myanmar young adults. This study fills the research gap by showing the effectiveness of group psychological intervention in enhancing subjective well-being of high school students in Myanmar. The study also supports the usefulness of PERMA Model applying positive emotion, meaning, and achievement can improve adolescent well-being. Furthermore, the study highlights practical implications for schools, counselors, and policy makers because the program is easy to run, low-cost, feasible, and culturally adapted. The key point is that this study highlights the importance of developing culturally adapted mental health programs in Myanmar. While there are still challenges such as shyness and discomfort among participants, this researcher believes careful facilitation and adaptation can overcome these challenges.

Limitations of the Study

Although the researcher worked carefully on this study, there are still some limitations to be addressed. Due to internet difficulty, the researcher has to use a convenience sampling method, which is a limitation for generalization of the population. Secondly, the intervention sessions were implemented only four times over one month and no further follow-up data were collected. This can be considered a limitation for reliability. Thirdly, the well-being of the students is assessed by self-report questionnaires, which may cause bias due to social desirability or misinterpretations. Lastly, the intervention was conducted online, which can reduce engagement of participants rather than in-person sessions.

Recommendations

Several recommendations can be proposed for future research and practice depending on the results and limitations. To give more accounts on generalization, future studies should consider implementing in both city and rural areas schools. In order to improve reliability, future follow-ups should be taken into consideration. To avoid self-report bias, the results should also come from teachers and students, which can strengthen validity as well. The government should also promote funding for school-based programs, increase awareness of adolescent mental health, and encourage to development of more culturally adapted guidelines for social-emotional learning.

Overall, this study shows that a culturally adapted, positive psychology-based group intervention can significantly enhance subjective well-being among high school students in Patheingyi, Myanmar.

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